

**ANTENNAL SENSILLA OF MALE DIASPIDIDAE (HOMOPTERA):
COMPARATIVE MORPHOLOGY AND FUNCTIONAL INTERPRETATION**

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ABSTRACT

The structure and ultrastructure of the antenna in males of several Diaspididae species was studied using light microscopy, and scanning and transmission electron microscopy. Several types of sensilla are described. Mechanoreceptors (one campaniform sensillum, some mechanoreceptive setae and Johnston's organ) were found in the scapus and pedicel, whereas three types of chemosensory sensilla, namely 'multiporous grooved' (MPG), 'multiporous pitted' (MPP), and 'single walled Wall Pore' (swWP) occur on flagellomeres. Under the light microscope, the MPG sensilla appear as sensilla trichodea, whereas the MPP are similar to sensilla chaetica. Some knobbed setae, found on the last flagellomere, have an aporous shaft, whereas the proximal calyx of the apical knob bears a thick distal cuticular end with a cribrate appearance. Following comparative observations it is hypothesized that the general organization of the sensilla is common to Diaspididae. Two sensillary patterns were recognized, with an attempt to use these data at the systematic level.

KEY WORDS: Coccoidea, Diaspididae, crystal violet, SEM, TEM, trichodeal pattern, chaetical pattern, *Unaspis euonymi*, *Aonidiella aurantii*, *Melanaspis inopinata*, *Aonidia lauri*, *Aspidiotus nerii*.

INTRODUCTION

Various publications deal with characteristics of the adult male Diaspididae, including exoskeletal features (Bustshik, 1958; Ghauri, 1962; El-Minshawy and Osman, 1973; Davidson and Miller, 1977; Miller et al., 1984; Nada and Mohammad, 1984; Bullington et al., 1989; Giliomee, 1990); internal morphology and anatomy (Theron, 1958; Swiderski, 1980; Robinson, 1990); and biological and behavioural aspects in connection with pest population control (see Rosen, 1990). However, very little morphological data are available on the antennal sensilla of male Diaspididae.

In addition to the intrinsic value of such data it is known that males Diaspididae are attracted to the female pheromone for mating and that the male sensilla are involved in sexual interaction.

Data on these sensilla will inevitably improve our knowledge of systematics and taxonomy, thereby improving the significance of these characteristics (Davies, 1981, 1983; Davies and Boratynski, 1979).

In this context, the aim of this paper is to show that: (i) all setae on male antennae of several Diaspididae species are sensilla that can be grouped in different types; (ii) setae and campaniform sensillum on the scape and pedicel have mechanosensory functions; (iii) Johnston's organ is placed in the pedicel; and (iv) all setae on the flagellum are chemosensilla.

The basiconic sensilla placed at the tip of the apical antennomere may be thermo-hygroreceptors, but were not studied in the present paper.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

The specimens used in this study were collected in the field as prepupae or pupae. The first emerging males were discarded to ensure that subsequent males used for the study were at least 6 hours old. *Unaspis euonymi* (Comstock) males were studied by all methods, whereas males belonging to other species were studied only by methods required for features that appear different from those of *U. euonymi*.

The chemosensilla were studied by light microscopy using a modified Slifer's method (1960) carried out on whole specimens fixed according to Karnovsky (1965).

The data on position, shape, length, number and orientation of sensilla were obtained from 15 specimens studied by light microscopy, using bright field and phase contrast, and from a few specimens studied by Scanning Electron Microscopy (SEM). Light microscopy specimens were prepared following a slightly modified Theron's (1958) method. SEM specimens were critical-point dried and then coated with gold-palladium with a sputter coater.

Transmission Electron Microscopy (TEM) studies were carried out on antennae of specimens fixed according to Karnovsky (1965), post-fixed in osmium tetroxide, dehydrated in EtOH, and embedded in araldite 502. Serial sections were obtained by using a diamond knife and counterstained with uranyl acetate (Robinson et al., 1987) and lead citrate (Reynolds, 1963).

The terminology used here is based on Berlese (1909, p. 678), Snodgrass (1935, pp. 510–549), Schneider (1964), Zacharuk (1980, 1985), Altner and Prillinger (1980) and Keil (1982). The term "cuticular layer" refers to the organization of mechanosensilla (McIver, 1985).

The following abbreviations are used in the figures:

AN — antennal nerve	Fl4 — fourth flagellomere
cD — ciliary constriction(s)	Fl5 — fifth flagellomere
CH — sensillum chaeticum	Fl6 — sixth flagellomere
CS — ciliary sinus	Fl7 — seventh flagellomere
CU — cuticle	Fl8 — eighth flagellomere
CU1 — external cuticular layer	GR — groove(s)
CU2 — middle cuticular layer	HE — hemocyte
CU3 — internal cuticular layer	IPS — intrapedicellar sinuses
DB — dendritic branches	Jm — joint membrane
DS — dendritic sheath	k — apical knob
Fl — flagellomere	Ks — knobbed seta
Fl1 — first flagellomere	M — mitochondrion(dria)
Fl2 — second flagellomere	Ma — matrix
Fl3 — third flagellomere	ML — microlamellae

MT	— microtubules or neurotubules	SC	— sheath cell(s)
MV	— microvilli	scp	— scape
NC	— nerve cell	SCP	— scolopidium
NU	— nucleus	SS	— sensillar sinus
oD	— outer dendritic segment(s)	Sts	— stained shaft
pdC	— pedicel	tb	— tubular body
Pe	— peg	TR	— tracheal branches or tracheole(s)
Pt	— pore tubules	Uss	— unstained seta
Puns	— proximal unstained segment		

RESULTS

Light and scanning electron microscopy

Unaspis euonymi. Antennomeres bear sensilla trichodea, sensilla chaetica and knobbed setae (Figs. 1–3). A few short, 11 μm (mean) long sensilla trichodea occur on the scapus and pedicellum. Furthermore, the pedicellum bears one round-shaped sensillum campaniformium, 4 μm in diameter (Fig. 4) located dorsally near the outer end of the antennomere. The setae and campaniform sensillum on the scapus and pedicellum do not absorb crystal violet.

Flagellomeres bear a large number of sensilla trichodea of two sizes: the longest are 46 μm (mean) long, and are located all around the flagellomere, whereas those of medium length are 24 μm (mean) long, and are located on the ventral surface of flagellomeres, from the 2nd to the 7th, directed towards the substrate on which the insect rests. The number of sensilla trichodea ranges from six (first flagellomere) to fourteen (last flagellomere). All sensilla trichodea on the flagellum absorb crystal violet, with the shaft appearing to be blue-violet, whereas the base of the seta retains its natural colour (Fig. 5).

The terminal flagellomere bears 4 sensilla chaetica 44 μm (mean) long, located near the distal end of the joint and directed to the front of the insect. Their shafts absorb crystal violet very well and turn deep blue, whereas a short proximal segment of the seta retains its natural colour (Fig. 6). This final flagellomere also bears 3 knobbed setae, 43 (mean) μm long, one of which is apical and directed to the front of the insect, whereas the others are subapical and directed latero-ventrally or latero-dorsally (Fig. 7). These sensilla absorb crystal violet, but the shaft is too thin for proper observation. The apical knob of these setae is divided into two halves by a transversal groove: the proximal one is calix-shaped, whereas the distal one is hemispherical with a slightly irregular surface (Fig. 8).

The tip of the final flagellomere, just at the base of the apical knobbed seta, bears two basiconic sensilla ca. 3 μm long and directed to the front of the insect (Fig. 9). It is difficult to confirm whether the latter absorb crystal violet, because of their minute dimension and their position.

Figure 10 summarizes data on the position, length, kind and staining properties by crystal violet of the antennal sensilla in *U. euonymi*.

Other species. Studies were carried out with males of *Aspidiotus nerii* Bouché (Figs. 11–13), *Aonidiella aurantii* (Maskell) (Fig. 14), *Melanaspis inopinata* (Leonardi) (Figs. 15–17) and *Aonidia lauri* (Bouché) (Figs. 18–20). The scape and pedicel of these species bear short sensilla trichodea; the pedicel bears also a campaniform sensillum.

Figs. 1-3. *Unaspis euonymi* (Comstock), male antenna. 1. General view and aspect of the antenna (SEM). 2. Drawn by camera lucida. 3. Arrangement of sensilla on antennomeres.

Figs. 4-9. *Unaspis euonymi* (Comstock), male antenna. 4. Campaniform sensillum on pedicel (SEM). 5, 6. Antennal setae stained with crystal violet (light microscope). 7. Setae at the tip of the last flagellomere (Flh) (SEM). 8. Knob of knobbed seta Flh14 (SEM). 9. Sensilla basiconica at the tip of last flagellomere (Flh) (SEM).

Fig. 10. *Unaspis euonymi* (Comstock). A diagrammatic illustration of the position, length, kind and staining properties with crystal violet of the antennal sensilla of the male antenna.

Figs. 11–13. *Aspidiotus nerii* Bouché, male antenna, sensilla stained with crystal violet (light microscope).

Figs. 14–20. Antennal sensilla of males. 14. *Aonidiella aurantii* (Maskell). 15–17. *Melanaspis inopinata* (Leonardi). 18–20. *Aonidia lauri* (Bouché). All stained with crystal violet (light microscope).

Aspidiotus nerii and *Aonidia lauri* have flagellomeres provided with sensilla trichodea of mostly similar length and shape, with the last flagellomere bearing sensilla chaetica and a small number of knobbed setae; *M. inopinata* and *A. aurantii* have sensilla chaetica in place of sensilla trichodea.

The setae on scape and pedicel and the sensillum campaniformium do not absorb crystal violet. Crystal violet stains the shaft of other setae as in *U. euonymi*.

Transmission electron microscopy

Short sensilla trichodea. The sections show a poreless uninnervated shaft connected to the antennomere by a strongly electrondense joint membrane that surrounds a bilayered cuticle. The outer homogeneous cuticular layer is connected to the shaft, whereas the inner granulous layer embeds a dendritic sheath containing a tubular body. Below these structures there is a sensillar sinus occupied by microvilli (Fig. 21).

Campaniform sensillum. A poreless trilayered cuticle constitutes the dome of this sensillum: the outer homogeneous layer is not separated from the median layer and the inner granulous layers bear a dendritic sheath with an almost centrally located tubular body (Figs. 22–25). The dome articulates by a strongly electrondense joint membrane; it includes also a sensillar sinus with some microvilli (Fig. 26).

Johnston's organ is made up of ten anfinematic scolopidia and is located in the pedicel (Fig. 26). Each scolopidium is connected to the outer margin of the 2nd antennomere, and there are numerous nuclei of nerve cells near the scolopidia.

Medium and long sensilla trichodea. The shaft has grooved and porous walls and is innervated by 2–3 dendritic branches, each bearing several neurotubules (Figs. 27–29). A granulous matrix fills the space around and among the branches and displays protubules.

Sensilla chaetica. The shaft is smooth, porous and innervated by 10–12 dendritic branches provided with neurotubules, whereas the matrix surrounding the dendritic branches is granular and strongly electrondense (Figs. 30, 33). Below the base of the seta there is a large sensillar sinus delimited by many microvilli and microlamellae (Figs. 31, 33). Deeper within the antennomere there is a ciliary sinus with a few microvilli, whereas within the sinus there are 3–5 ciliary constrictions (Figs. 32, 33).

Proximal sections show nerve cells whose projections innervate sensilla chaetica (Fig. 34).

Knobbed seta. The shaft is aporous with a very thick, homogeneous wall. The lumen of the seta is filled with a moderately electrondense substance that surrounds a more electrondense subcentral area (Fig. 35).

The calyx in cross sections shows intrusions of the substance in the cuticular wall (Fig. 36). These intrusions become massive just under the hemispherical half of the knob (Figs. 37–39) where the substance looks fringed, and reaches the outer cuticular layer. The cuticle of the distal end of the knob appears bilayered: the outer layer is thin, whereas the inner is cribrous (Figs. 40, 41).

Below the base of the apical knobbed seta, within the last antennomere, there is a tubular body surrounded by a dendritic sheath and a sensillar sinus provided with microvilli (Fig. 42).

The observations on the campaniform, short sensilla trichodea, other trichodea, sensilla chaetica and knobbed seta are summarized in Figs. 43–47.

Figs. 21–25. *Unaspis euonymi* (Comstock). 21. Cross section of the base of a short sensillum trichodeum on the scape. 22–25. Tangential sections of the dome of the campaniform sensillum on pedicel.

Fig. 26. Oblique cross section of pedicel of male *Unaspis euonymi* (Comstock). Campaniform sensillum at the top of the picture.

Figs. 27-29. *Unaspis euonymi* (Comstock), male antenna, sections of shaft of sensilla trichodea on flagellomeres: 27, cross section at the tip; 28, longitudinal near the base; 29, cross section in the middle.

Figs. 30–31. *Unaspis euonymi* (Comstock), male antenna. 30. Cross section in the middle of the shaft of sensillum chaeticum. 31. Cross section under the base of a sensillum chaeticum at the level of the sensillary sinus.

Figs. 32–33. *Unaspis euonymi* (Comstock), male antenna. 32. Cross section below the base of sensillum chaeticum more proximal than in Fig. 31. 33. Cross section of a flagellomere at the level of the sinuses of three sensilla chaetica.

Fig. 34. Cross section of a flagellomere of *Unaspis euonymi* (Comstock) at the level of nerve cells innervating sensilla chaetica.

Figs. 35–40. *Unaspis euonymi* (Comstock), male antenna, cross sections of apical knobbed setae: 35, in the middle of the shaft; 36, at the proximal end of the calyx; 37, 38, at the level of the groove between calyx and hemispherical half; 39, at the level of the hemispherical half; 40, cuticular layer of the hemispherical half.

Figs. 41–42. *Unaspis euonymi* (Comstock), male antenna. 41. Longitudinal sections of the knob of the apical knobbed seta. 42. Cross section at the tip of the terminal flagellomere.

Figs. 43–45. *Unaspis euonymi* (Comstock), male antenna, schematic illustrations. 43. Campaniform sensillum. 44. Short sensillum trichodeum. 45. Medium and long sensillum trichodeum.

Figs. 46-47. *Unaspis euonymi* (Comstock), male antenna, schematic illustrations. 46. Sensillum chaeticum. 47. Knobbed seta.

DISCUSSION AND CONCLUSION

This study shows that all setae on the antennae of males of several species of Diaspididae are sensilla, which may be grouped into five types: short, medium and long sensilla trichodea, sensilla chaetica and knobbed setae. In addition one campaniform sensillum, Johnston's organ and two sensory pegs were observed on the antennae.

Short sensilla trichodea show only a mechanosensory structure (Schwartzkopff, 1964; McIver, 1975, 1985) located under the base of the shaft. The insertion point of the setae and their direction led us to hypothesize that these sensilla function to sense the relative position of the scape towards the head and of the pedicel to the first flagellomere in the male antenna of Diaspididae.

Medium and long sensilla trichodea belong to 'multiporous grooved' (MPG of Zacharuk, 1980, 1985) or 'single walled Wall Pore' (swWP of Altner and Prillinger, 1980). This type of sensilla are considered to be olfactory. On the basis of the position, orientation and number of sensilla on each flagellomere, we hypothesize that medium and long sensilla trichodea react to short- and medium-distance range semiochemicals.

Sensilla chaetica are of the 'multiporous pitted' (MPP of Zacharuk, 1980, 1985) or 'single walled Wall Pore' (single walled WP of Altner and Prillinger, 1980) type, with an olfactory function. The location of these sensilla exclusively on the last antennomere led us to hypothesize that sensilla chaetica react to long-range semiochemicals having a directional significance.

Knobbed setae are not typical sensilla, and their ultrastructure is not very clear, possibly due to difficulties in fixation or embedding steps as a result of the very long aporous shaft. Hence, the following interpretation should be regarded a preliminary.

Relevant aspects are: the presence of a mechanosensory unit; the shaft being filled with a matrix present up to the apical knob where the outer cuticular layer is very thin and the matrix seems to reach the surface in places that look similar to pores; and the position of these sensilla and their outgrowing over trichodea and chaetica. All these data suggest that the knobbed setae have a gustative function, but the absence of neurotubules in the shaft and in the apical knob prevents a definite conclusion.

The campaniform sensillum has a mechanosensory structure for the detection of cuticular stress (McIver and Siemicki, 1975). The subcircular shape of the dome proved to be useful in detecting stress coming from all directions (Moran et al., 1971; Zill and Moran, 1981a, b; Zill et al., 1981).

The scolopidia in the pedicel are considered to be Johnston's organ (Howse, 1968). In the males of Diaspididae this organ may detect relative wind speed during flight.

Sensillary pattern and Diaspididae taxa

The annulated antenna of *U. euonymi* males show a characteristic pattern of flagellar sensilla, due to either the number of sensilla on each flagellomere, or the orientation and type of sensillum.

On the basis of these features it is possible to recognize a trichodeal pattern (e.g. in *Aspidiotus*) and a chaetical pattern (e.g. in *Melanaspis*), respectively, characterized by the presence or absence of sensilla trichodea on the flagellum.

Based on published descriptions of male Diaspididae, I have recognized similar antennal patterns at higher level of taxa. The illustrations presented by Bustshik (1958), Ghauri (1962),

Davidson and Miller (1977), Miller et al. (1984), Nada and Mohammad (1984), and Bullington et al. (1989) led us to recognize that males of the Parlatorini and Rugaspidiotini have only a chaetial pattern, whereas males of the Aspidiotinae show both patterns, and males of the Diaspidini and Odonaspidini display only a trichodeal pattern.

In future studies the flagellar sensillary pattern in more species of Diaspididae will be investigated by light microscopy and crystal violet staining. Further, we intend to study the position and number of nerve cells of medium-sized and long sensilla trichodea; show the nature and function of basiconic sensilla, if possible in connection with those of female antenna of Diaspididae; and try physical methods of fixation (Steinbrecht, 1980) to obtain better data on the ultrastructure of knobbed setae.

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